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Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Prabhat, a very early-maturing rice variety released in Bihar, India

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Very early-maturing rice varieties are needed before and after floods in northern Bihar, in the wet season, and for the irrigated summer crop harvested before the monsoon. These varieties are also suitable for upland conditions when rain is inadequate.

We began work in the early 1980s to breed suitable varieties after receiving some materials from IIRI. SBR34-69-1 (IR9201-30-1-3-1-3, derived from IR3033-521-1/IR2061-464-2/IR36) matched the desired duration. It was included in state varietal trials in summer and then in the wet season. It was marginally superior in yield to checks Pusa 2-21 and Pusa 33 across 11 environments in the summer (Table 1), though it matured nearly 2 wk earlier. It yielded significantly more than Sattari or Heera (75-80 d duration) during 1989-93 wet seasons.

SBR34-69-1 has droopy lower leaves, making a canopy over the ground that suppresses weed growth (Table 2).

SBR34-69-1 has been named Prabhat. It is semidwarf, matures in 85 d in wet season, and is resistant to bacterial blight. Its grains are long-bold. ■

Table 2. Weed-suppressing ability of SBR34-69-1 in variety × weed interaction trial at Sabour, India, 1994.

Culture	Weed dry weight (g/m ²)	
	Set I (July)	Set II (August)
SBR34-69-1	4.6	8.7
SBR36-70-1	9.5	32.0
ES29-3-3	13.9	21.2
ES21-2-3	13.2	18.5
ES28-3-1	12.2	19.2
ES1-1-2	12.1	15.7
CV (%)	20.1	17.0
LSD (5%)	4.7	3.3

Table 1. Yield performance of SBR34-69-1 at different sites in Bihar, India, 1984-93.

Year	Site	Yield (t/ha)		LSD (5%)	CV (%)
		SBR34-69-1	Check ^a		
<i>Summer</i>					
1984	Patna	1.4	1.6	0.09	13.0
	Pusa	1.8	1.6	0.61	19.5
	Sabour	2.7	2.2	0.50	15.7
1988	Patna	5.0	4.0	0.71	17.5
	Pusa	2.5	2.2	0.43	19.2
1989	Patna	1.3	1.5	0.96	20.0
	Pusa	1.7	2.5	0.58	12.1
	Sabour	2.6	2.1	1.18	26.4
1990	Sabour	2.1	1.2	0.60	14.2
1991	Sabour	2.1	1.2	0.63	14.6
1992	Sabour	2.7	2.2	0.60	14.5
	Pooled mean	2.3	1.8		
<i>Wet season</i>					
1989	Pusa	3.4	2.7	0.88	21.9
	Sabour	2.5	1.9	0.43	11.7
	Dhangain	3.7	2.7	0.72	7.2
1990	Pusa	2.5	1.2	0.88	12.9
	Sabour	2.6	1.4	1.04	19.7
1991	Pusa	2.5	1.1	0.24	13.1
	Dhangain	4.1	2.2	0.78	15.4
1992	Pusa	2.4	1.8	0.42	10.4
	Sabour	2.0	1.2	1.08	11.1
	Dhangain	3.3	2.5	0.56	12.6
1993	Pusa	4.0	1.8	0.61	15.5
	Patna	3.8	2.3	ns ^b	
	Sabour	1.6	1.1	0.85	16.8
	Bikramganj	5.0	4.3	1.39	17.1
	Pooled mean	3.1	2.1	1.7	

^aPusa 2-21 or Pusa 33 for summer. Sattari (1st column) or Heera (2nd column) for wet season. ^bns = not significant.

Zhefu No. 7, a mutant indica rice variety of short duration for central and eastern China

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Short-duration varieties are preferred for use in the early season (Apr-Jul) in the double-cropped area of central and eastern China. From 1986 to 1991, about 1.2-1.3 million ha of this area were planted each year to the leading short-duration variety, Zhefu 802. Zhefu No. 7 was released in July 1994 as an alternative to Zhefu 802. Both have similar

yield potential and growth duration, but Zhefu No. 7 has superior grain quality and blast resistance. Zhefu No. 7 was bred by mutation induction in which seeds of medium-duration variety Erjiufong were exposed to a 30,000 rad dose of ⁶⁰Co gamma rays. Erjiufong, once a popular variety, was highly susceptible to cold and low K content in the soil, which restricted its cultivation. Zhefu No. 7, however, has a 4-5 d shorter growth duration and superior tolerance for cold and low K compared with Erjiufong, making it more adaptive to double-cropped areas. Some differences in morphoagronomic characters exist between Zhefu No. 7 and Erjiufong (Table 1).

Table 1. Yield and morphoagronomic characters of Zhefu No. 7 and its parent Erjiufong at Yuhang, Zhejiang Province, China, 1990.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Spikelet fertility (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)
Zhefu No. 7	5.7	77.0	19.5	93.7	88.5	22.3
Erjiufong	5.6	80.8	20.2	103.6	88.0	22.2

The average yield of Zhefu No. 7 was 6.1 t/ha in most areas, and 7 t/ha in a few areas. No significant difference in yield

was detected between Erjiufong and Zhefu No. 7 (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Yield performance^a of Zhefu No. 7 and check Erjiufong in regional tests in Zhejiang Province, China, 1990.

Site	Locations (no.)	Zhefu No. 7 yield (t/ha)	Erjiufong yield (t/ha)	Increase over check (%)
Hangzhou	13	5.97 ± 0.49	6.24 ± 0.49	-4.4
Fuyang	7	5.39 ± 0.40	5.28 ± 0.36	+2.0
Shaoxin	4	7.01 ± 0.27	6.78 ± 0.25	+3.3
Ningbo	22	6.56 ± 0.61	6.34 ± 0.59	+3.5
Linhai	10	5.37 ± 0.40	5.17 ± 0.34	+3.8

^aNo significant difference was detected at 0.05 level between Zhefu No. 7 and Erjiufong in any of the regional tests.

PNR162 (Renu), an early rice variety with superfine grain and multiple resistances

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After several years in coordinated trials, PNR162 was recommended for release for West Bengal and Orissa states in India during the National Rice Workshop in 1989. The Government of Uttar

Pradesh released it for irrigated areas in Sep 1993. Its potential yield is 8 t/ha in northwestern India and about 9 t/ha in summer (boro) season in West Bengal (Table 1).

The variety has superfine grain, multiple resistances to pests, and other desirable characters (Table 2). It has become popular in many other parts of India because it can fit into various crop rotations. Its moderate cold tolerance makes it suitable in the high altitude

Table 1. Average grain yield (t/ha) of PNR162 in various trials, 1986-92.

Site	PNR162	IR36	Ratna	Pant 4	Saraju 52
Zone 3 ^a	3.5	2.9	-	-	-
Zone 4 ^a	3.9	3.6	-	-	-
Zone 6 ^a	4.8	4.3	-	-	-
Kerala ^b	3.3	2.1	3.0	-	-
Tamil Nadu ^b	5.6	5.2	4.4	-	-
Punjab ^b	4.9	4.2	4.7	-	-
Haryana ^b	7.9	7.3	7.1	-	-
Jammu and Kashmir ^a	5.3	2.7	-	-	-
Tripura ^a	4.5	3.6	-	-	-
Uttar Pradesh ^c	5.0	-	-	5.1	4.4

^aCoordinated trials, 1987 wet season. ^bCoordinated trials, 1986 wet season. ^cStation trials, 1991-92.

Table 2. Quality characters of PNR162.

Character	PNR162	Ratna (check)
Kernel length (mm)	7.0	6.6
Kernel breadth (mm)	2.0	2.1
Length-breadth ratio	3.5	3.2
Hulling (%)	79.0	75.0
Milling (%)	72.6	69.5
Head rice recovery (%)	56.0	55.0
Alkali value	4.0	6.0
Abdominal white	Absent	Absent

plains of Manipur, Arunachal Pradesh, and parts of Jammu and Kashmir.

In coordinated, state, and on-farm trials, the variety outperformed national and local checks (Table 1). Its nonshattering trait provides an advantage over Ratna, a popular variety of similar duration. PNR162 was developed from the cross Jaya Mutant (gamma radiation induced)/Basmati 370 through selection in two diverse environments. ■

Shanyou Wan 3, a medium-maturing, indica hybrid rice

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Minghui 63, an elite late-maturing rice restorer line, was used as the female parent in a cross with early-maturing rice restorer line 26 Zhaizao in 1984 autumn. The hybrid was planted that winter in Hainan, China. We treated the seeds harvested from the F₁ plants in 1985 with ⁶⁰Co gamma ray (D = 177 R/min, D = 2.2 × 10⁴ rad), planted the seeds, and conducted pedigree selection. In 1989, an early-maturing mutant plant was chosen and testcrossed with Zhenshan 97 A, with the testcross F₁ hybrid performing very well. This hybrid, named Shanyou Wan 3, was tested in 1990. Its restorer line was named Wan 3. The Crop Variety Release Committee of Hunan Province, China, approved Shanyou Wan 3 for commercial production in Jan 1994.

In 1990, Shanyou Wan 3 was tested in a multilocation trial and yielded an average 7.5 t/ha, 13.0% more than check hybrid Weiyou 64, and 10.3% more than check hybrid Shanyou Gui 33 (both significant at 1% level). It matured 5 d earlier than Shanyou Gui 33 and 4 d later than Weiyou 64. The average grain yield of Shanyou Gui 33 was 7.8 t/ha, 14.9% more than that of check Weiyou 64 in the 1991 Loudi Prefectural Rice Variety Regional Trial, Hunan Province (4 hybrids over 5 locations) (see table). In the 1991 All-China Indica Hybrid Rice Regional Trial, it ranked first in grain yield, with an average of 6.6 t/ha, and matured in 119 d. Compared with the check Shanyou Gui 33, its maturity duration, grain yield, and daily grain yield were 3.7 d longer, and 2.7% and 6.1% more, respectively. In 1992, Shanyou Wan 3 was cultivated for demonstration on 1,333 ha in several provinces and showed high-yielding ability. In 1993, it was planted on 44,667 ha.

Shanyou Wan 3 is 95-105 cm tall. It has stiff straw, good lodging tolerance, and adaptability to heavy fertilization. The panicles are 22-24 cm long with 120-130 spikelets per panicle. The seed setting rate is 80-85% and the 1,000-grain